

Polymetallic complexes. Part-LXXXII. Bis-bidentate and bis-tridentate azodye dimeric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}

Bipin B. Mohapatra* and S. K. Saraf

P. G. Department of Chemistry, G. M. (Autonomous) College, Sambalpur-768 004, India

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Twelve dinuclear complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with the new azodye ligands bis[4,4'-(2'-hydroxynaphthylazo)phenyl]ether having $\text{ON}=\text{ON}$ donor atoms and [2,2'-di[3-(2'-hydroxyphenylazo)-4'-hydroxyphenyl]propane having $\text{ONO}=\text{ONO}$ donor atoms have been synthesized.

In continuation of our work on inorganic polymers¹, the present work reports the synthesis of one bis-bidentate (LH₂) and one bis-tridentate (L'H₄) azodye ligands and their twelve metal complex dimers.

(LH₂)

(L'H₄)

Results and discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) indicate that the metal complexes have the compositions [M₂LCl₂(H₂O)₆], [M'₂LCl₂(H₂O)₂], [M₂L'(H₂O)₆] and [M'₂L'(H₂O)₂], where, M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, M' = Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, LH₂ = bis[4,4'-(2'-hydroxynaphthylazo)phenyl]ether and L'H₄ = 2,2'-di[3-(2'-hydroxyphenylazo)-4'-hydroxyphenyl]propane. All the complexes are amorphous in nature, have high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents. There is no mass-loss of the complexes even if heated upto 120°, confirming the above stoichiometry of the complexes. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from the Λ_m values (5.3–6.7 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal %		μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found	(Calcd.)	
LH ₂	Brown	–	–	–
L'H ₄	Brown	–	–	–
[Co ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Brown	14.4	(14.6)	5.0
[Co ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₆]	Brown	18.8	(19.0)	5.1
[Ni ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Red	15.9	(16.1)	–
[Ni ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	Red	20.1	(20.2)	–
[Cu ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Red	15.4	(15.7)	1.81
[Cu ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₆]	Brown	17.8	(18.1)	1.78
[Cd ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	White	26.3	(26.7)	–
[Cd ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	White	30.5	(30.8)	–
[Zn ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	17.2	(17.4)	–
[Zn ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	Grey	20.3	(20.5)	–
[Hg ₂ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Red	39.2	(39.5)	–
[Hg ₂ L'(H ₂ O) ₂]	Grey	44.1	(44.4)	–

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

In the IR spectra of the ligands, broad bands appear at 3027–3052 and 2920–2964 cm^{-1} which may be ascribed to intermolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding. Disappearance of these bands in the metal complexes indicates the bonding of phenolic and naphtholic OH groups to the metal ions. The ligand bands at 1490 (LH₂) and 1510 cm^{-1} (L'H₄) can be assigned to naphtholic and phenolic C–O vibrations, respectively, and in the metal complexes these bands are observed at ~1480 and ~1500 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating the bonding of the ligands through naphtholic and phenolic oxygen atoms². The sharp band appearing at 1619 (LH₂) and at 1611 cm^{-1} (L'H₄) can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ vibration and a decrease of this band by 5–10 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates indicates the bonding of one of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal atoms³. In the metal chelates, broad bands appear at ~3349–3436 cm^{-1}

followed by sharp peaks at ~ 832 and 730 cm^{-1} assignable to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations, respectively, indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules⁴ in the complexes. The appearance of bands at ~ 414 (M–N) and $552\text{--}565\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M–O) in the complexes confirms the bonding of the ligand to the metal ions⁵.

In the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes, four bands appear at 8872 , 17824 , 19640 and 32145 cm^{-1} (LH_2) and 8865 , 17750 , 19728 and 32370 cm^{-1} ($\text{L}'\text{H}_4$). The last band of each series may be attributed to a CT-band and the first three bands can be attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$,

$\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively⁶. The ligand field parameters $10D_q = 895$ (888) cm^{-1} , $B = 723.2$ (725.5), $\beta_{35} = 0.744$ (0.747), $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.009$ (2.002), $\sigma = 35.75$ (33.86) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes. In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes, two bands appear at ~ 16475 and $\sim 17355\text{ cm}^{-1}$, assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_{1g}$ transitions, respectively, which support a square-planar geometry for the complexes⁷. This formulations is further supported by the diamagnetic nature of the complexes. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show one broad band at $\sim 13560\text{--}$

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of the complexes

Compd.	Unit cell parameter	Volume \AA^3	Density g/ml	n	Possible geometry
$[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	20 = 27.81, 30.00, 32.50, 35.00, 37.50, 40.00, 41.56, 41.88, 45.00, 46.56, 48.13, 50.00, 54.38, 59.38, 61.56, 65.00, 69.38, 74.06, 76.88, 78.75, 81.63, 84.38, 85.63, 92.19, 95.00, 97.50 $A = 10.677$, $B = 7.385$, $C = 7.254$, $\alpha = 90.00$, $\beta = 98.754$, $\gamma = 90.00$	559.16	2.08	1.0	Monoclinic
$[\text{Co}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$	20 = 23.50, 25.67, 29.00, 30.00, 35.00, 35.33, 36.17, 38.33, 38.83, 39.67, 40.50, 42.00, 46.67, 48.00, 50.67, 56.00, 58.67, 59.00, 60.00, 60.83, 61.33 $A = 7.148$, $B = 11.562$, $C = 5.095$, $\alpha = 90.00$, $\beta = 104.237$, $\gamma = 90.00$	408.15	1.63	0.5	Monoclinic
$[\text{Co}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	20 = 20.50, 22.67, 23.67, 24.33, 25.33, 26.67, 27.83, 29.33, 30.17, 31.00, 31.67, 33.33, 34.33, 35.00, 35.83, 36.83, 39.33, 40.17, 41.00, 41.67, 42.33, 43.00, 43.67, 44.83, 47.67, 49.67, 50.67, 53.00, 53.50, 55.83, 65.17 $A = 12.830$, $B = 17.537$, $C = 4.086$, $\alpha = 90.00$, $\beta = 90.00$, $\gamma = 90.00$	919.32	2.79	2.0	Orthorhombic

14870 cm^{-1} with maximum at $\sim 14340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in support of a distorted octahedral configuration⁸.

The Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic in nature. The μ_{eff} values of the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are found to be at ~ 5.0 and 1.80 B.M. , respectively, indicating octahedral configuration of the complexes⁹.

The ESR spectra of the copper complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$ have been recorded at X-band at RT. In the first complex, the g_{av} is found to be 2.0710 by applying Kneubuhl's method¹⁰. This type of spectrum may be due to dynamic or pseudorotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion. In case of the second complex, the geometry around the Cu^{II} ion in the unit cell is tetragonal (elongated octahedral) with $g_{\perp} = 2.0778$ and $g_{\parallel} = 2.2898$. The symmetry parameter G is found to be 3.7249 which suggests the absence of exchange interaction among magnetically equivalent ions in the unit cell¹¹. The g_{\parallel} is a function for representing covalency. The g_{\parallel} value for the Cu^{II} complex is found to be less than 2.3, indicating covalent nature of the complex¹². The trend observed for the complex, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.0023) indicates that the unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectrum of the ligand LH_2 shows a complex pattern at $\delta 7.05\text{--}8.09$ due to 20 phenyl protons. The peak observed at $\delta 9.15$ can be assigned to two phenolic protons. In the spectrum of the ligand $\text{L}'\text{H}_4$, a complex pattern is observed at $\delta 6.71\text{--}7.25$ due to 14 phenyl protons. The sharp singlet peak at $\delta 1.25$ indicates the presence of 6 methyl protons attached to a carbon atom ($\text{CH}_3\text{--C--CH}_3$).

The X-ray diffraction study (powder method) of the compounds $[\text{Co}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$, $[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ have been indexed in X-ray diffractometer and the unit cell parameters have been calculated with the help of computer from the indexed data. The unit cell parameters like A , B , C , α , β , γ and ν suggest the probable geometry of the complex (Table 2). The density of the compound is measured by flotation method in a saturated solution of KBr , NaCl and with CCl_4 separately. The number of formula units per unit cell is calculated from the relation¹³, $n = dN\nu/M$, where d is the density of the compound, N the Avogadro number, ν the volume of the unit cell and M the molecular weight of the compound. The calculated value of n is 0.5 for $[\text{Co}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]$, 1.0 for $[\text{Zn}_2\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and 2.0 for $[\text{Cd}_2\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. Both Zn and Co complexes are found to be monoclinic and Cd complex is found to be orthorhombic. The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are suggested to be four-coordinated having tetrahedral geometry based upon the analytical, IR and conductance data.

Hence the azo dye LH_2 behaves as bis-bidentate ligand and $\text{L}'\text{H}_4$ as bis-tridentate ligand. Both the ligands form dimeric complexes, being bonded through phenolic oxygen and azo nitrogen atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. or E. Merck make. Metal, nitrogen and chlorine were estimated by standard methods. Conductivity measurement in dimethylformamide was made using a Toshniwal CL 01-06 conductivity bridge. Magnetic moment was measured at room temperature by Gouy method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on an IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} M in DMF) using a Higler-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer and ESR spectra on a E_4 -spectrometer. XRD (powder pattern) of the complexes was recorded on a Phillips PW 1130/00 diffractometer.

The azo dye ligands were synthesized by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chlorides obtained from 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ethers (0.01 mol, 2.08 g) and *o*-aminophenol (0.02 mol, 2.18 g) with alkaline solution of β -naphthol (0.02 mol, 2.88 g) and 2,2'-di(4'-hydroxyphenyl)propane (0.01 mol, 2.28 g) respectively at $0\text{--}5^\circ$.

The complexes: A mixture of ethanolic solution of the metal chloride and the ligand solution in ethanol was heated at $60\text{--}70^\circ$ for $\sim 1\text{ h}$. On cooling, pH of the solution was raised to around 7 by adding conc. ammonia dropwise with stirring. The solid complexes thus separated were washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

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